

check remained in diapause. Aestivation ended sooner under artificial flooding than with artificial rainfall. Moths emerged 18-21 d after watering in the artificial flooding regime and 29-45 d after watering in the artificial rainfall regime (see table). □

Morphometric measurements of green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Stal) head and body during development

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We made morphometric measurements of the head and body of GLH during development of seven individuals. The results are in the table. □

Effect of artificial watering on diapause of white stem borer larvae, Sukamandi, 1990.

Simulated source of water	Observation	Source of prepupa ^a	
		Karawang	Sukamandi
Flooding	Prepupal duration	60 DAH	104 DAH
	Pupae transformed	5-8 DAW	4-8 DAW
	Moths emerged	18-21 DAW	18-21 DAW
Rainfall	Prepupal duration	52 DAH	96 DAH
	Moths emerged	29-45 DAW	29-45 DAW

^aDAH = days after harvest, DAW = days after watering.

Average length and width of the head and body of GLH at different stages.

	Head		Body	
	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Length (mm)	Width (mm)
1st nymphal instar	0.150 (0.131-0.171)	0.210	0.857 (0.802-0.921)	0.336 (0.315-0.368)
2d nymphal instar	0.215 (0.184-0.236)	0.236 (0.210-0.263)	1.088 (1.026-1.131)	0.381 (0.368-0.407)
3d nymphal instar	0.273 (0.236-0.302)	0.289 (0.263-0.315)	1.355 (1.289-1.394)	0.535 (0.486-0.578)
4th nymphal instar	0.457 (0.421-0.473)	0.557 (0.526-0.605)	2.849 (2.710-3.078)	1.041 (1.026-1.065)
5th nymphal instar	0.457	0.621 (0.578-0.657)	3.548 (3.342-3.684)	1.157 (1.078-1.210)
Adult male	0.342 (0.315-0.368)	0.731 (0.684-0.815)	3.981 (3.736-4.210)	1.390 (1.263-1.710)
Adult female	0.373 (0.342-0.394)	0.810 (0.763-0.842)	4.736 (4.473-4.868)	1.661 (1.526-1.894)

A new blister mite pest of rice in the Philippines

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Aceria saccharini (Acari: Eriophyidae), a blister mite pest of rice, has been reported on sugarcane in Indonesia; Australia; Taiwan, China; and India. It damages leaf sheaths and transmits streak virus disease. In 1988, it was reported to have transferred to rice in Sulawesi, Indonesia. Now it has been found in Central and Southern Luzon, Philippines.

Injury on rice is similar to that caused by thrips, and damage symptoms can be confused with tungro. Feeding produces white, chlorotic, shallow, gall-like pustules. Blisters vary in length (0.20-18 mm) and width (0.01-10 mm). The long proboscis of the mite probes vertically into the upper or lower epidermis of the leaf, lacerating tissues and rupturing both epidermal and parenchymous tissue cells.

Mites from different localities differ in color, from cream to pale yellow or

orange pink. The orange pink form is more prevalent. The adult mite is microscopic in size (0.16 + 0.04 mm long, 0.05 ± 0.002 mm wide) (see figure). Mites moving on the leaf surface can be seen with the naked eye.

With magnification, the adults appear wormlike with a shield-shaped head. The body bears two pairs of slender legs anteriorly. All legs have claws, with 6-7 protruding feathered ray hairs each. The abdomen is annulated with 78-82 rings and three pairs of ventral setae. Eggs are spherical 0.05 mm in diameter, pale yellow turning to orange pink when about to hatch.

The pale yellow larva has a droplet-like shape with a large globular anterior, tapered posterior, and a pair of moderately long anterior legs. The protonymph, twice the size of larva, is whitish to light yellow with a thin layer of golden yellow hairs laterally. Both are orange pink when mature.

We monitored mite densities in 14 fields during the wet season. Three leaves each were sampled from the bottom,

A. saccharini adult (middle, 18×) transparent egg (right midlateral, 12×), and larva (bottom one-fifth, 18×).

middle, and top plant areas at seedling, maximum tillering, panicle initiation, and ripening stages. Ten samples per growth stage were bagged separately or placed in vials with 80% alcohol.